

ANTICOAGULANT PROPERTIES OF ENDOPHYTIC FUNGI FROM CERTAIN MEDICINAL PLANTS OF THE CHATKAL BIOSPHERE RESERVE

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Relevance: In the current era of modern technologies, the supply of medicines is an important issue in the treatment of diseases caused by heredity, gene mutations, cell membrane disorders of higher organisms, climate degradation, and other causes, including in the situation caused by the coronavirus. One of the complications remaining after the COVID-19 disease, which has spread throughout the world, is the state of platelet aggregation. This naturally increases the demand for the production of blood thinners (for example, heparin, cleacsan, etc.). In the context of the current pandemic, one of the urgent problems is the search for cost-effective substitutes for such drugs using the anticoagulant properties of endophytic fungi, their screening and recommendation for pharmaceuticals and medicine.

Purpose of the research: To study the diversity of endophytic fungi that produce anticoagulant properties of medicinal plants of Uzbekistan.

Methods and techniques: About 1300 plant species are found in the territory of the Chatkal Biosphere Reserve of Uzbekistan, of which 200 species are medicinal plants. Medicinal plants are the main source of endophytic fungi, which possess various antioxidant, anticancerogenic, including anticoagulant properties.

In accordance with the goal, for the study of biological activity, endophytic fungi were isolated from plants growing in the Chatkal Biosphere Reserve, which have been used in medicine since ancient times in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, skin diseases, joint and gastrointestinal diseases among various peoples, such as medicinal lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis*), great chamomile (*Chelidonium majus*), bird cherry (*Polygonum aviculare*), tripartite thistle (*Bidens tripartite*), fragrant basil (*Ocimum basilicum*), mint (*Mentha piperita*), saffron (*Crocus sativus*), and climbing tamarisk (*Thymus serpyllum*).

Results: More than 55 samples of endophytic fungi were isolated from the leaves, stems, and roots of the selected plants. Based on morpho-cultural characteristics, the isolated samples can be classified into the following 10 genera: *Acremonium*, *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Cuningamella*, *Fusarium*, *Gliocladium*, *Mycelia*, *Mucor*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*. All strains have been placed in the collection of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan for their intended use.

When studying the anticoagulant properties of metabolites prepared and extracted from the studied endophytic fungi (prothrombin time in blood plasma according to the Quick method), high anticoagulant activity (blood clotting time 300 seconds) was detected in 29 strains.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that the anticoagulant activity detected in endophytic fungi isolated from medicinal plants was the main step in the work on their use as a pharmaceutical raw material.